

Correction to: A tale of flawed e-cigarette research undetected by defective peer review process

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In this article the authors name Riccardo Polosa, Konstantinos Farsalinos was incorrectly written as Polosa Riccardo, Farsalinos Konstantinos.

The original article has been corrected.

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